

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No6(6)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 472 sahifa,
22-iyun, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyuu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

“Kitobxonlar klubi” modelining ingliz tili to‘garak mashg‘ulotlarida o‘quvchilarning kognitiv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari.....	10
Madaminova Gulzira Gulamkadirovna	
Bo‘lajak pedagoglarning kasbiy faoliyatida suggestiv yondashuvning o‘rni	14
Arolov Davronjon Davlataliyevich	
Akmeologik yondashuv asosida maktabgacha ta‘lim direktor o‘rinbosarlarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish	19
Asatullayeva Sitora Dilmurod qizi	
Hozirgi o‘zbek tilida neologizmlarning tarixi va bugungi kun taraqqiyoti.....	22
Bektosheva Mehinbonu Abdumalik qizi	
Maktabgacha ta‘lim tashkilotlari bolalarida jamoada ishlash ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	26
Djurayeva Dilfuza Nuriddin qizi	
Korpus lingvistikasi vositalari yordamida bo‘lajak ingliz tili o‘qituvchilarining til tahlili ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	30
Eshonqulova Sarvinoz Yashinovna	
Talabalarning shaxsiy sifatlarini rivojlantirishda sun‘iy intellektning o‘rni va ahamiyati.....	35
Hojiyeva Nasiba Bahodirovna	
Logopedik mashg‘ulotlarni tashkil etish va rejalashtirish moduliga oid mustaqil ta‘lim topshiriqlarini integrativ modellashtirishning innovatsion texnologiyalari.....	39
Ibroximova O‘g‘iloy Inomjon qizi	
Jismoniy tarbiya darslarida ortiqcha vaznli bolalarga differensial yondashuvning ahamiyati	43
Yuldashev Bobirjon Noibjon o‘g‘li	
Maktabgacha ta‘lim tashkilotida xalq og‘zaki ijodi vositasida bolalarning axloqiy sifatlarini shakllantirishning ahamiyati.....	48
Muradxanova Munisaxon Ikrom qizi	
Bo‘lajak psixologlarda altruistik xulq motivlarini rivojlantirishning psixologik imkoniyatlari	54
Nusratova Mexriniso Baxshilloevna	
Inklyuziv ta‘lim tushunchasi va uning zamonaviy pedagogik paradigmalar tizimidagi o‘rni.....	59
Pulatova Dilfuza Azamkulovna	
Magistrlarda “Imposter sindromi”ni yengish orqali kreativ salohiyatni rivojlantirishning psixologik mexanizmlari.....	66
Qayumov Baxtiyor Zokirjon o‘g‘li	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalar nutqining fonematik rivojlanishi	70
Qurbonova Sevara Suyunovna	
Mikrobiologiya ta‘limida individual pedagogik texnologiyalarni joriy etish mexanizmlari	74
Raxmatov Oxunjon Soibjonovich	
“Estetik tarbiya”, “kreativ kompetensiya”, “estetik tarbiya mexanizmlari” tushunchalarining konseptual asoslari.....	79
Saidova Feruza Akramovna	
Zamonaviy ta‘lim jarayonida neyropedagogika yordamida nutqiy ko‘nikmalarni rivojlantirish.....	84
Sidiqova Yulduz Sobirovna	
“So‘nggi jadid” Begali Qosimovning ilmiy-pedagogik merosi.....	88
Toxirova Dilshoda Inom qizi	
Ona tili darslarida o‘qib tushunish ko‘nikmasini rivojlantiruvchi mashq va topshiriqlar ustida ishlash	92
Turg‘unova Nilufar Muxiddin qizi	
Ingliz, golland va o‘zbek tillaridagi frazeologizmlarning lingvostatistik xususiyatlari.....	96
Xaydarova Go‘zalxon	

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda hayotiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda yumshoq ko'nikmalarning ahamiyati.....	101
<i>Xolmatova Dilshoda Sherali qizi</i>	
Farzandlarda kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirishda oilaning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	105
<i>Yusupova Diloromxon Sabirdjanovna</i>	
Yoshlarda tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish orqali sotsial manipulyativ ta'sirlarga psixologik barqarorlikni shakllantirish.....	109
<i>Qosimova Sarvinoz Baxtiyorovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda modellashtirish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga ko'maklashadigan faoliyat usullari	114
<i>Abdurazzaqov O'ktam Abduqayumovich</i>	
Dizartriya shakllarining klinik-patogenetik tahlili va differensial diagnostikasi	120
<i>Axmedova V. T.</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda fanlararo yondashuvga asoslangan integrativ topshiriqlar ishlab chiqishning uslubiy asoslari.....	127
<i>Elmurodova Inoyat Abdumutalibovna</i>	
Deviant xulq-atvorli o'smirlar ijtimoiylashuvining psixologik determinantlari.....	132
<i>Elov Ziyodullo Sattorovich</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida talabalar o'quv natijalarini baholashning pedagogik modeli.....	138
<i>Ernazarov Mirzohid Yo'ldosh o'g'li</i>	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalarida biokimyo fanini raqamli texnologiyalar asosida o'qitish metodikasi	145
<i>Mamadaliyeva Zarina Raxmat qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda kognitiv tilshunoslikni joriy etish masalalar	150
<i>Mamatova Gulshan Amankulovna</i>	
Doston musiqiy merosini o'rganishni uslubiy takomillashtirish mazmuni.....	153
<i>Qo'shayev Ilhom Axtamovich, Nasirova Sevinch Ismatovna</i>	
"Elektr yoritish" fanida mustaqil ta'limning zamonaviy shakllari.....	157
<i>Nasretdinova Feruza Nabiyeвна</i>	
Maktabgacha va maktab yoshidagi bolalarda sog'lom turmush tarzi madaniyatini shakllantirish	162
<i>Nazarova Dildora Asatovna, Kuchkorova Robiya Shuxrat qizi</i>	
Dual ta'limda oliy ta'lim va maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning mazmuni.....	167
<i>Qoraboyeva Zohidaxon To'lanboyevna, Tursunbayeva Sevara Abdullo qizi</i>	
A Methodological Model for Developing Pedagogical Reflection in Pre-Service EFL Teachers.....	172
<i>Rahimberdiyeva Maftuna Rakhimberdi kizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda sog'lom turmush tarzining kasbiy kompetentlikka ta'siri	177
<i>Raximova Saboxat Qaxramon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda interaktiv texnologiyalar va faol ta'lim metodlarining samaradorligi	182
<i>Safarova Nigora Nasilloevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim jarayonida interfaol usullarning mazmuni, turlari va funksional ahamiyati.....	190
<i>Safarova Soliha Ilhomovna</i>	
Talabalarni ma'naviy tarbiyalash jarayonida diagnostik metodlardan samarali foydalanishning ahamiyati... 196	
<i>Saotmuratova Zebo Yuldash qizi</i>	
Musiqqa ta'limida interfaol metodlardan foydalanishning didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	200
<i>Saparov Raxim Muratbayevich</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi tarbiyalanuvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish ijtimoiy zarurat sifatida.....	204
<i>Xolmatova Yodgoroy Baxtiyorjon qizi</i>	
Energetika fanlarini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning pedagogik afzalliklari.....	208
<i>Zoxidov Iqboljon Zokirjonovich</i>	
Методическая модель контекстуального обучения в формировании лингвокультурной компетенции при обучении русскому языку в национальных группах	213
<i>Рустамова Ферузaxon Махмуджановна</i>	

Integrating Artificial Intelligence into EFL Academic Writing Instruction: Opportunities, Challenges, and Pedagogical Implications.....	218
<i>Allamurodov Elyor Tursun ugli</i>	
Sahna nutqida adabiy tur va janrlarning metodik talqini.....	223
<i>Dilrabo Jumanova</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi ta'lim ekotizimi: imkoniyatlar va xavflar	227
<i>Oqil Ochilov Lutfullo o'g'li</i>	
Z avlod bilan ishlashda ta'lim va tarbiyaga oid zamonaviy tendensiyalar	232
<i>Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich</i>	
Talabalarni ma'naviy tarbiyalash jarayonida diagnostik metodlardan samarali foydalanishning ahamiyati...	235
<i>Saotmuratova Zebo Yuldash qizi</i>	
Tarixiy-ilmiy materiallar va zamonaviy texnologiyalar integratsiyasi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining geometrik tafakkurini rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	239
<i>Toshpulatova Mamura Ismailovna, Mannonova Dilafro'z Ravshan qizi</i>	
Davlat-xususiy sherikchilik asosidagi maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini boshqarish va muvofiqlashtirish ...	244
<i>Xakimov Abdug'ulom Soyibjonovich</i>	
Ingliz tilini boshqa sohadagilarga o'qitishda grammatik jihatlar	247
<i>Ataboyeva Guliruxsor Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Methodological Foundations for Developing Environmental Education Through the Integration of Climate Change Education Into Biology Lessons in General Secondary Schools.....	250
<i>Abdurakhmanova Iqbolkhon Yulchiyevna</i>	
Sharq va G'arb mutafakkir olimlarining oila va farzand tarbiyasi borasidagi qarashlari	255
<i>Berdiyeva Dilnoza A'zamovna</i>	
Ommaviy sport turlari yordamida ayollarni sog'lom turmush tarziga yo'naltirishda ilmiy yondashuv	258
<i>Charos Axmadova</i>	
STEAM integratsiyasi orqali maktab o'quvchilarida tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish	262
<i>Choriyor Maxmatraimov Eshmamatovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim kafedrasida bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni innovatsion-metodik faoliyatga tayyorlashni transformatsion boshqarish texnologiyasi	267
<i>Djalalov Baxromjan Begmurzayevich</i>	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida yosh ota-onalarda yolg'izlik hissining namoyon bo'lishiga ta'sir etuvchi ijtimoiy-psixologik va etnopsixologik omillar	272
<i>Erimmetova Nafisa Bahromovna</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim muhitida talabalarning ijtimoiy-psixologik adaptatsiyasi va uning strategiyalari	279
<i>Haqberdiyeva Dinora Qobil qizi</i>	
Maktab direktorlarining moliyaviy boshqaruv kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	283
<i>Karimov Jaxongir Abdunabiyevich</i>	
Jadidlar merosiga e'tibor: tarixiy xotira va ma'naviy tiklanish omili.....	287
<i>Madaminova Shaxodat Shomurotovna</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ta'limdagi o'rni va nutqni baholashdagi imkoniyatlari.....	293
<i>Mahmudova Maftuna Aktam qizi</i>	
Effectiveness of Simulator Technologies in Pilot Training: an Experimental Study	297
<i>Maksudov Ilhomjon Turgunboy o'g'li</i>	
Yangi O'zbekistonda o'qituvchi maqomining huquqiy kafolatlari va pedagogik faoliyat samaradorligi.....	301
<i>Menlibayeva Azima Oralbayevna, Oralbayeva Aziza</i>	
Raqamli jamiyat sharoitida ong transformatsiyasining falsafiy jihatlari.....	305
<i>Muxitdin Nazarov</i>	
10-11-sinf o'quvchilarida o'qishdan yozuvga o'tish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishning bosqichli metodik tizimi ...	310
<i>Nazarova Shoiraxon Abdumo'min qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim paradigmasida "potensial" tushunchasi: shaxsning rivojlanishga qaratilgan ichki imkoniyatlari, bilim, ko'nikma, qobiliyat va kompetensiya.....	314
<i>Qurbonova Gulmira Alisher qizi</i>	

Deffenbacherning driving anger scale metodi asosida haydovchilarning agressiv xulq-atvorining psixologik xususiyatlarini jinslar kesimida o'rganish	318
<i>Rahim Usmonov Raxmonali o'g'li</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning pedagogik-psixologik mexanizmlari.....	323
<i>Sadoqat Sarmanova Shermahmatovna</i>	
Vizual axborot: paydo bo'lish tarixi, qo'llanish sohalari va ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati.....	328
<i>To'g'izboyev Faxriddin Ulashovich</i>	
Fizika darslarini tashkil etishning mazmuni, mohiyati va didaktik tamoyillari.....	334
<i>Turabova Lobar Xusen qizi</i>	
Ekstrakorporal urug'lantirish orqali tug'ilgan bolalarda xotiraning rivojlanishi	339
<i>Usmonova Xusnora Ergashovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining emotsional barqarorligini shakllantirish.....	344
<i>Yusupova Diloromxon Sabirdjanovna</i>	
Milliy va xalq o'yinlari vositasida talabalarni sog'lomlashtirish.....	347
<i>Axmedov Gayratjon Kosimovich</i>	
Деонтология медицинского персонала: этико-профессиональные ориентиры в условиях современной медицины.....	350
<i>Бабаджанова Гулчехра</i>	
Формирование творческого восприятия учащихся на уроках музыки.....	355
<i>Габдульманова Ильнура Минисламовна</i>	
Qizlar tarbiyasida maktab va mahalla hamkorligi monitoring tizimini takomillashtirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	358
<i>Abdurazoqova Marg'uba Muxammad qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachilarida iqtisodiy tushunchalarni shakllantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	362
<i>Ergashova Dilafro'z</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kasbiy karyerani shakllantirishning metodologik asoslari	365
<i>Hayitova Sarvinov Mahmudovna, Ilmiy rahbar: Ashirova Sojida Baxromovna</i>	
Pedagogical and Methodological Foundations for Developing an Interactive Mobile Application for Teaching English to Preschool Children (Based on the Solobee Project).....	368
<i>Khurshida Kuchkarova</i>	
O'spirinlarda kiberbullingning profilaktikasi va psixokorreksion imkoniyatlari.....	373
<i>Ibodova Gulimehr Inoyat qizi</i>	
Pedagogical Factors and Didactic Conditions for Developing Communicative Competence in Future Teachers.....	378
<i>Mirzayeva Gulshan Azamatovna</i>	
Musiq ta'limida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	382
<i>Altmisheva Maftunabonu Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
The Importance of the Concept of Discursive Competence in Teaching English.....	386
<i>Mukhamatjonova Diyora Rustam qizi</i>	
Koxlear implantli bolalarni ta'lim jarayoniga moslashtirishning korreksion-pedagogik asoslari.....	390
<i>Najimova Muhabbat</i>	
Alfa avlod uchun internet xavflari klassifikatsiyasi metodlarini ishlab chiqish klassifikatori	393
<i>Ahralov Shavkat Sulaymonovich, Ahrorova Sevara Sulaymon qizi</i>	
Aqli zaif o'quvchilar ta'limida sensor integratsiyaning pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	398
<i>Tajibayeva Shaxnoza Abdumuxtorovna</i>	
Koxlear implantatsiyali o'quvchilarning psixologik-pedagogik rehabilitatsiyasi samaradorligini oshirishda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish.....	401
<i>Yuldasheva Saodat Utkurovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni zamonaviy pedagogik fikr-g'oyalardan kreativ foydalanishga tayyorlashning ustuvor tamoyillari.....	406
<i>Akbarova Feruza Uktamjonovna</i>	

Biologiya ta'lim bosqichida noan'anaviy integratsiyalashgan darslar jarayonida CLIL texnologiyfsini joriy etish	410
Azimov Ibragimjon Toshpulatovich, Toshpo'latova Nigina Ibrohimjon qizi	
Onlayn ta'lim muhitida didaktik kompetensiyani takomillashtirish yo'llari	416
Kushimova Mahbuba Janibekovna	
Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida koxlear implantga ega bolalarning eshituv-nutqiy faoliyatini tashkil etishning pedagogik asoslari.....	420
Mirzayeva Umidaxon Inamovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni inklyuziv ta'limga tayyorlashda pedagogik shart-sharoitlar va tamoyillar tizimi.....	423
Omanqulova Shohida Nematillo qizi	
Talabalarda axborot-psixologik tahdidlarni oldini olishning psixologik imkoniyatlari.....	426
Ramazonov Jahongir Djalolovich	
Changes in the Structure and Strength of the Aluminum Alloys SAV-1 Irradiated With Fast Neutrons	431
S. A. Baytelesov, F. R. Kungurov, G. N. Turdieva, I. V. Papushki, A.V. Galushko	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash kompetensiyasini baholashga diagnostik model asosida yondashuv.....	438
Suvankulova Malika Baxtiyor qizi	
"Integratsion mexanizm" – integratsiyani tadqiq etishdagi muhim yo'nalish sifatida	444
Xayitov Lazizbek Rustamjon o'g'li	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalari talaba qizlarining somatotipik va funksional xususiyatlariga ko'ra tabaqalashtirilgan individual fitnes mashg'ulotlari uslubiyati.....	447
Ziyatov Muhammad Namazovich	
Проблемы формирования координационных способностей у дошкольников с нарушением слуха и рекомендации по их развитию	451
Закирова Сарвиноз Баратовна, Кобулова Шахризода Равшан кизи	
Uy ta'limi sharoitida o'quvchilarning o'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-metodik asoslari.....	455
Sodiqova Nurgul Tursunboyevna	
Paradzyudoni rivojlantirishning dolzarb muammolari va ularni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	459
Berdiyev Sherzod Ochilovich	
Pedagogik antropologiya Ushinskiy talqinida	462
Ochilova M. P.	
Using Concept Checking Questions to Improve Vocabulary Retention in English Language Classrooms: Evidence from Uzbekistan	468
Ramazonov Jasurbek Safar O'g'li	

CHANGES IN THE STRUCTURE AND STRENGTH OF THE ALUMINUM ALLOYS SAV-1 IRRADIATED WITH FAST NEUTRONS

S. A. Baytelesov

F. R. Kungurov

G. N. Turdieva

I. V. Papushki

A.V. Galushko

Institute of nuclear physics, academy of sciences,
settlement Ulugbek, Tashkent, 100214, Uzbekistan
joint institute for nuclear research (jinr), dubna,
Moscow region, 141980, Russia

Abstract: The aluminum alloy SAV-1 was studied before and after neutron irradiation with doses ranging from 10^{16} to 10^{18} n/cm². The measurements were carried out using volumetric methods, namely small-angle neutron scattering and neutron diffraction. A loading machine was employed to investigate the correlation between structural changes and the strength characteristics of the samples. It was found that changes in the strength characteristics of aluminum alloys were associated with modifications occurring at the grain boundaries during irradiation. The obtained experimental data allow us to conclude that the SAV-1 alloy represents an interstitial solid solution, and its strength changes nonlinearly depending on the radiation dose.

Key words: aluminum alloy SAV-1, neutron irradiation, neutron scattering, microstructure, phase composition.

Annotatsiya: SAV-1 alyuminiy qotishmasi 10^{16} – 10^{18} n/sm² diapazonidagi neytron nurlanishi ta'siridan oldin va keyin tadqiq qilindi. O'lchovlar hajmiy usullar, ya'ni kichik burchakli neytron sochilishi va neytron difraksiyasi yordamida amalga oshirildi. Namunalardagi strukturaviy o'zgarishlar hamda mustahkamlik xususiyatlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqlash maqsadida yuklash mashinasidan foydalanildi. Aniqlanishicha, alyuminiy qotishmalarining mustahkamlik xususiyatlaridagi o'zgarishlar nurlanish jarayonida donalar chegaralarida yuz beradigan modifikatsiyalar bilan bog'liqdir. Olingan eksperimental ma'lumotlar SAV-1 qotishmasi kiritma qattiq eritma ekanligini hamda uning mustahkamligi nurlanish dozasiga bog'liq holda chiziqli bo'lmagan tarzda o'zgarishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: SAV-1 alyuminiy qotishmasi, neytron nurlanishi, neytron sochilishi, mikrostruktura, fazaviy tarkib.

Аннотация: Алюминиевый сплав SAV-1 был исследован до и после нейтронного облучения дозами от 10^{16} до 10^{18} н/см². Измерения проводились объемными методами, а именно методом малоуглового рассеяния нейтронов и нейтронной дифракции. Для изучения взаимосвязи между структурными изменениями и прочностными характеристиками образцов использовалась испытательная нагрузочная машина. Установлено, что изменения прочностных характеристик алюминиевых сплавов связаны с модификациями, происходящими на границах зерен в процессе облучения. Полученные экспериментальные данные позволяют сделать вывод о том, что сплав SAV-1 представляет собой твердый раствор внедрения, а его прочность изменяется нелинейно в зависимости от дозы облучения.

Ключевые слова: алюминиевый сплав SAV-1, нейтронное облучение, рассеяние нейтронов, микроструктура, фазовый состав.

INTRODUCTION

SAV-1 is characterized by a low degree of activation during irradiation and maintains high corrosion resistance in steam-water environments. However, these materials are susceptible to aging and possess a relatively low melting point. Their application as load-bearing elements in reactor cores, even in the case of the most heat-resistant alloys based on sintered aluminum powder, is limited to temperatures of 450-500°C. Despite this

limitation, the high thermal conductivity of aluminum allows the use of aluminum-based products capable of operating under significant thermal loads when an appropriate geometry is applied. The high manufacturability of aluminum alloys makes it possible to fabricate thin-walled products with complex profiles, such as protective claddings of fuel elements, pipelines, tanks, experimental channels, auxiliary reactor-core structures, and matrices for dispersion fuel rods and self-burning absorbers operating under a wide range of radiation fields [1].

The aluminum alloy SAV-1 (Al-Mg-Si) is the principal structural material used for core elements and fuel rod cladding in the WWR-SM reactor of the Institute of Nuclear Physics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan (INP AS RUz). The reactor was built and commissioned in 1959 and continues to operate successfully due to the high-performance characteristics of the materials used, particularly aluminum alloys. The phase composition of alloys of this type (avial alloys) depends on the concentration ratio of the primary alloying elements, magnesium and silicon. Therefore, the main phases in SAV-1 consist of α (Al), Mg_2Si , and Si. In addition to these primary phases, intermetallic compounds such as $AlSiFe$, $Al_{10}Mn_2Si$, and $AlSiMnFe$ may also be present, depending on the chemical composition. During neutron irradiation, nuclear reactions result in an increase in silicon content through the $Al(n,\gamma)Si$ reaction [2].

By interacting with atoms in the alloy, silicon can alter the phase balance and induce stresses that contribute to the formation of micropores and microcracks, leading to degradation of the material's mechanical properties. Therefore, the atomic structure of these alloys is investigated to diagnose such defects, which are considered primary precursors to material failure [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies on the radiation resistance of structural materials are being conducted by leading researchers at major nuclear research centers worldwide [1], [3], [9], [10], [12], [13], [14], [15]. The SAV-1 alloy has been extensively studied; however, further clarification is required regarding the changes in its physical and mechanical properties as functions of fast-neutron fluence and temperature. Since reactor operational safety depends directly on these parameters and structural characteristics, the application of neutron scattering and diffraction techniques is particularly promising. Therefore, we investigated the structural states of SAV-1 before irradiation and after neutron irradiation with doses ranging from 10^{16} to 10^{18} n/cm².

The measurements were performed using volumetric methods, namely small-angle neutron scattering and neutron diffraction. To determine the correlation between structural states and macroscopic strength characteristics, a loading machine was employed. The samples were irradiated at the IBR-2 reactor in Horizontal Channel No. 3. The average reactor power was 2 MW. The thermal neutron flux at the moderator surface was approximately 10^{16} n/cm²·s (time-averaged), while the maximum pulse flux reached approximately 10^{16} n/cm²·s. It should be noted that no preliminary thermal treatment of the samples was performed before irradiation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The measurements were carried out at room temperature using a uniaxial loading machine LM-20 (FLNP JINR, Dubna), designed to apply mechanical loading to samples at various strain rates under PID control. The machine allows both tensile and compressive loading with forces up to 30 kN. A key advantage of the system is the practically backlash-free transmission of load to the specimen. In the present experiment, the applied load was 10 kN, while the motor step rate was set at 0.25 μ m/s. Compression tests: cylindrical specimens with a diameter of approximately 6 mm and a length of 10-12 mm. Tensile tests: cylindrical specimens with a diameter of approximately 6 mm and a length of 72-78 mm.

Table 1: The elemental composition of unirradiated and neutron-irradiated samples of SAV-1

Fluence n/cm ²	Al %	Si%	Mg%	Fe%	Ni%	Cu%	Mn%
Before irradiation	98,27	0,5	1,06	0,14		0,02	0,01
Before irradiation [3]	97,2-98,5	0,6-1,2	0,45-0,9	0,2	0,03	0,01	0,01
After irradiation 10¹⁷	97,77	1,1	0,82	0,28		0,02	0,01
After irradiation 10¹⁸	97,32	1,75	0,62	0,30		0,01	-
After irradiation 10¹⁹ [4]	97,09	2,05	0,53	0,32		0,01	
After irradiation 10²⁰ [4]	96,86	2,35	0,45	0,33		0,01	

In SAV-1 alloys, the principal alloying elements are Mg and Si. Their concentrations increase as a result of nuclear reactions: the silicon concentration increases through the $Al(n,\gamma)Si$ reaction, while the magnesium concentration increases through the $Si(\gamma,\alpha)Mg$ reaction. As can be seen from the data presented in the table,

neutron irradiation of aluminum alloys causes not only radiation-induced damage but also changes in the concentrations of alloying elements. When the concentration of alloying elements exceeds the solubility limit, a new phase precipitates. This process, together with the migration of impurity atoms toward defect accumulations (such as dislocations, grain boundaries, and other structural defects), significantly influences changes in the physical and mechanical properties of the material [3]. To investigate the structure averaged over the entire sample volume, neutron diffraction experiments were performed using the Fourier Stress Diffractometer (FSD) installed at Channel 11A of the IBR-2 pulsed reactor at the Frank Laboratory of Neutron Physics, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research (JINR, Dubna). The measurements were carried out on a series of SAV-1 aluminum alloy samples (see Table 2). A specialized correlation technique, employing a high-speed Fourier chopper to modulate the intensity of the primary neutron beam together with the Reverse Time-of-Flight (RTOF) data acquisition method, made it possible to obtain diffraction spectra with high resolution ($\Delta d/d \approx 2 \times 10^{-3}$ at a scattering angle of $2\theta = 140^\circ$ and $\Delta d/d \approx 4 \times 10^{-3}$ at $2\theta = \pm 90^\circ$) over a wide range of interplanar spacings. This provided the accuracy required to detect small shifts and broadenings of diffraction peaks [5, 6].

Table 2: The parameters of irradiated and non-irradiated samples of SAV-1 alloy, for which measurements were carried out in the FSD device

№	Fluence, n/cm ²	Notes
1	0	Cylinder (∅6 mm, h =50 mm)
2	0	Cylinder (∅6 mm, h=50 mm)
3	0	Powder (vanadium container, ∅5 mm, h=50 mm)
4	0	Disk (∅ 17 mm, h=3,2 mm)
5	10 ¹⁶	Disk (∅ 17 mm, h=3,5 mm)
6	10 ¹⁷	Disk (∅ 17 mm, h=2,9 mm)
7	10 ¹⁸	Disk (∅ 17 mm, h=3,2 mm)

To evaluate differences in the sizes and shapes of dispersed particles ranging from 1 to 100 nm, small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) data obtained using the YuMO time-of-flight spectrometer at JINR (Dubna) were analyzed [7, 8]. The measurements were performed at sample-to-detector distances of 5.28 m and 13.04 m, providing a scattering vector range (Q) from 0.006 to 0.3 Å⁻¹, corresponding to structural features ranging from approximately 2 to 100 nm. The diameter of the sample exposed to the neutron beam was 17 mm. The obtained neutron scattering spectra were corrected for neutron absorption, sample thickness, and background scattering from the substrate. Calibration was performed using a vanadium reference sample, and the neutron scattering intensity was normalized to absolute units (cm⁻¹).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

During the mechanical testing of the samples, the following strength characteristics were determined: ultimate tensile strength, σ_{ts} (temporary resistance); yield strength, σ_y (physical yield point); 0.2% offset yield strength, $\sigma_{0.2}$ (technical yield point); proportional limit, σ_{pl} ; elastic limit, σ_{el} ; true tensile strength, S_k ; relative elongation, δ ; reduction of area (constriction), ψ .

Table 3: The main mechanical properties of stretching SAV-1 before and after irradiation in the IBR-2 reactor with different fluences

Fast neutron fluence, n/cm ²	σ_{ts} , MPa	σ_y , MPa	$\sigma_{0.2}$, MPa	σ_{pl} , MPa	σ_{el} , MPa	S_k , MPa	δ , %	ψ , %
before irradiation	160,4	154,8	154,3	108,6	117,9	147,4	18	15
10 ¹⁶	190,7	185	180	83,4	110	119	16	16
10 ¹⁷	165	159	159	83,4	100	107	17	16
10 ¹⁸	175	162	162	84	105	110	13,5	7
SAV-1 [9] before irradiation							16,5	
3,5•10 ²²							2,5	

The observed difference between the lattice strength of irradiated and non-irradiated SAV-1 alloy samples can be readily explained by assuming that SAV-1 behaves as an interstitial solid solution. This assumption is justified by the fact that silicon and magnesium do not form stable chemical compounds with aluminum [3].

Accordingly, the atoms of the principal alloying elements, silicon and magnesium, occupy interstitial positions within the aluminum crystal lattice, leading to an increase in the dimensions of the unit cells in which they are located. As a result, local lattice distortions occur, affecting the mechanical and structural properties of the alloy.

Figure 1: F is the stress stretching parameter which cause the elongation in the fluidity area (kN), L is the length of the sample at the moment of rupture.

Samples: ■ –unirradiated ; ◆ - $10^{16}n/cm^2$; ● - $10^{17}n/cm^2$; ▼- $10^{18}n/cm^2$.

Table 4: Effect of Neutron Fluence on the Mechanical Properties of SAV-1 Aluminum Alloy

Fluence/cm ²	Relative elongation $\delta\%$	Stress-deformation Q kg/mm ²
0	16	18,16
10^{16}	16,4	19,3
10^{17}	16,8	16,9
10^{18}	13,5	19,1
0 [10]	22,1	14
10^{17} [10]	25,2	15,2
10^{22} [10]	18,5	20,1

A pronounced crystallographic texture was observed in almost all investigated samples. This feature is most likely associated with the texture already present in the original material from which the specimens were manufactured. The measured diffraction spectra were processed using the Pawley method [11]. As a result, the crystal lattice parameters of the material and the parameters describing the dependence of diffraction peak widths on the interplanar spacing were determined (Figs. 3 and 4). The dimensions of the unit cells within the crystal lattice of the solid solution vary from one region of the lattice to another. Therefore, only the average value of the lattice parameter can be considered. It is well known [3] that, in interstitial solid solutions, dissolved atoms occupy interstitial sites within the crystal lattice and cause local distortions of the crystal structure of the matrix material. The magnitude of these distortions is relatively large compared with the size of the interstitial sites occupied by impurity atoms. Consequently, the volume of distorted unit cells increases despite the relatively low concentration of impurities.

As a result, a noticeable increase in the average lattice parameter of the alloy occurs, accompanied by a corresponding expansion of the unit-cell volume during the formation of the interstitial solid solution. This effect was confirmed experimentally. Consequently, the crystal lattice of the alloy is characterized by a specific configuration in which some interstitial sites are occupied by alloying atoms, whereas others remain vacant. Based on the analysis of diffraction peak broadening relative to the instrumental resolution function of the diffractometer, the microstrain values averaged over all observed (hkl) reflections were determined (see [5]).

Figure 2: Neutron Diffraction Pattern of the SAV-1 Aluminum Alloy at 293 K

Figure 3: The diffraction spectrum of the aluminum alloy SAV-1 (sample No. 1), processed by the method of Pauli [11]. Experimental points, calculated and difference in curves, positions of diffraction peaks are shown.

Figure 4: The parameters of the crystal lattice (a) and average microstrain (b) for the samples of SAV-1. The doses of irradiated samples are indicated.

Figure 5 illustrates the small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) intensity as a function of the scattering vector Q for aluminum alloy samples before irradiation and after irradiation with neutron doses of 10^{16} , 10^{17} , and 10^{18} n/cm². According to the relationship $D \approx 2\pi/Q$, the scattering vector range of $0.0063 \text{ \AA}^{-1} < Q < 0.3 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ corresponds to a structural size hierarchy of $2 \text{ nm} < D < 100 \text{ nm}$. The SANS results indicate that no significant structural changes occur within the size range of 2 to 100 nm, as all scattering curves remain within the limits of experimental uncertainty. Therefore, neutron irradiation does not induce noticeable diffusion of individual elements or precipitation of secondary phases either within the grains or at the grain boundaries. It should be noted that neutrons possess a high penetration capability in matter, whereas X-rays are effectively absorbed within a depth of approximately 100 μm . Consequently, it can be concluded that the average volume changes in structural features ranging from 2 to 100 nm are insignificant.

The neutron diffraction results obtained for the size range $0.05 \text{ nm} < D < 1 \text{ nm}$ are in good agreement with the conclusions drawn from the small-angle neutron scattering data. These findings appear to contradict the results obtained by X-ray diffraction, electron microscopy, and macroscopic strength measurements. This discrepancy can be explained by the fact that the latter methods provide information primarily from the surface layers of the samples. The atomic lattice at grain boundaries is more susceptible to neutron-induced damage than the lattice within the grain interior. As a result, subtle structural modifications occurring at grain boundaries may remain undetectable by bulk-sensitive techniques such as neutron diffraction and small-angle neutron scattering, while they can be observed using electron microscopy and X-ray diffraction. It is precisely these localized changes at grain boundaries that lead to significant variations in the mechanical strength of the material. Figure 5. Dependence of the small-angle neutron scattering intensity on the scattering vector Q for aluminum alloy samples: (a) before irradiation; (b) after irradiation with a dose of 10^{16} n/cm²; (c) after irradiation with a dose of 10^{17} n/cm²; and (d) after irradiation with a dose of 10^{18} n/cm². The small-angle neutron scattering method was applied to investigate the supramolecular structure of SAV-1 alloy samples in both the initial state and after irradiation with fast neutron fluences up to 1×10^{18} n/cm². The results revealed a decrease in the volume fraction of scattering structures (pores) with radii of 40–50 nm in the irradiated material, which was largely compensated by an increase in the total fraction of similar structures with radii below 20 nm. The neutron scattering results correlate well with the mechanical testing data and the observed changes in the elemental composition of the irradiated alloys.

CONCLUSION

The observed difference in lattice parameters between cylindrical samples and disk-shaped specimens is most likely associated with deformation introduced during the manufacturing process of the disk samples. The level of microstrain in the investigated samples was generally low and appears to be related to residual deformation introduced into the original billet during the rolling process. An exception was sample No. 3 (powder sample), which exhibited a relatively high level of microstrain. This behavior can be explained by the significant plastic deformation of the alloy during the preparation of the powder from aluminum chips. No clear dependence of either the lattice parameter or the microstrain level on radiation dose was observed for samples 4–7, indicating the absence of significant structural changes at relatively low irradiation doses.

The effectiveness of the combined application of neutron diffraction and small-angle neutron scattering techniques was demonstrated through the performed experimental investigations. The average volumetric characteristics determined by small-angle neutron scattering (2–100 nm) and neutron diffraction (0.01–1 nm) exhibited only minor changes after irradiation up to 1×10^{18} neutrons/cm². It was established that even minor modifications occurring at grain boundaries during irradiation can lead to measurable changes in the strength characteristics of aluminum alloys. Thus, the analysis of the obtained experimental results allows us to conclude that the SAV-1 alloy behaves as an interstitial solid solution and that its mechanical strength changes nonlinearly with increasing radiation dose.

References:

1. Lebedev, V.M., Lebedev, V.T., Ivanova, I.N., Orlov, S.P., & Orlova, D.N. (2010). The structure of aluminum alloys irradiated with reactor neutrons. *Physics of the Solid State*, 52(5), 1021–1027.
2. Sturken, E.Z. (1979). Radiation effects in aluminum alloys. *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, 82, 39–45.
3. Hoffman, A., Didyk, A.Yu., Shteke, V., Khaevska, E., Wagner, T., & Semina, V.K. (2004). Investigation of radiation-induced structural changes in aluminum alloys. *JINR Communication No. P14-2004-174*, Dubna, Russia, pp. 1–10.
4. Salikhbaev, U.S., Baytelesov, S.A., Khidirov, I.G., Kungurov, F.R., et al. (2008). Effect of reactor irradiation on the microstructure and microhardness of aluminum alloys SAV-1 and AMG-2. *Alternative Energy and Ecology*, 9(65), 105–109.
5. Bokuchava, G.D. (2018). Neutron Fourier stress diffractometer FSD at the IBR-2 pulsed reactor. *Crystals*, 8(8), 318. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst8080318>

6. Bokuchava, G.D., & Papushkin, I.V. (2018). Neutron time-of-flight stress diffractometry. *Journal of Surface Investigation: X-ray, Synchrotron and Neutron Techniques*, 12(1), 97–102. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S102745101801024X>
7. Ostanevich, Y.M. (1988). Time-of-flight small-angle scattering spectrometers on pulsed neutron sources. *Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics Symposium*, 15, 91–103.
8. Kuklin, A.I., Islamov, A.K., & Gordeliy, V.I. (2005). Two-detector system for small-angle neutron scattering instrument. *Neutron News*, 16(3), 16–18.
9. Karasev, V.S. (1989). Mechanical and plastic properties of SAV-1 alloy after long-term operation in the WWR-M reactor. *Problems of Atomic Science and Technology. Series: Radiation Damage Physics and Radiation Materials Science*, 2(49), 39–40.
10. Maksimkin, O.P., Yarovchuk, A.V., Turubarova, L.G., Aulova, D.S., et al. (2011). Influence of neutron irradiation on intergranular corrosion and corrosion cracking of low-alloyed aluminum alloy SAV-1. *Problems of Atomic Science and Technology*, 2, 108–115.
11. Pawley, G.S. (1981). Unit-cell refinement from powder diffraction scans. *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, 14, 357–361.
12. Mavlyutov, A.M., Kasatkin, I.A., Murashkin, M.Yu., et al. (2015). Influence of microstructure on the physical and mechanical properties of an Al–Mg–Si alloy nanostructured by severe plastic deformation. *Physics of the Solid State*, 57(10), 1998–2004.
13. Murayama, M., Hono, K., & Saga, M. (1998). Atom probe studies on the early stages of precipitation in Al–Mg–Si alloys. *Materials Science and Engineering A*, 250, 127–132.
14. Kim, Y.S., Cho, B.J., & Sohn, D.S. (2015). Thermal conductivity modeling of U–Mo/Al dispersion fuel. *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, 466, 576–582.
15. Minitz, A., Shtechman, A., et al. (1998). Mechanical properties and microstructure of neutron-irradiated cold-worked Al-6063 alloy. *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, 252, 79–88.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №6(6)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.